

Establishment of wheat following lowland rice in east India

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A field experiment was conducted on the economic feasibility of relay wheat cropping in the lowland rice ecosystem at Pusa (Bihar) during 1993-94 and 1994-95. It used a split-plot design with three replications and six methods of wheat crop establishment in the main plot and three seed rates in the subplot. The soil was silty clay, pH 8.4 (1:2.5, soil:water), with initial nutrient status of 262 kg N ha⁻¹, 34.5 kg P ha⁻¹, and 110 kg K ha⁻¹. A long-duration traditional aman rice variety, Sudha, was transplanted under normal practices in both the years and the wheat variety Sonali was grown according to treatments listed in the table. In relay cropping, wheat seeds were broadcast 10-12 d before harvest in standing rice to avoid delayed seeding. Three seed rates, i.e., 125, 150, and 175 kg ha⁻¹ were with all subplot treatments. Wheat crops were also raised by normal practices, except for relay and zero tillage. In relay cropping, fertilizer was used after the first irrigation.

In wheat cultivated in the lowlands, *Chenopodium album*, followed by *Launia pinnatifide*, is the dominant weed where

wheat is tilled. In relay cultivation, *L. pinnatifide* is the dominant weed in early growth and later *Cyperus rotundus* and *Cynodon dactylon* become dominant. More or less the same trend is observed in all plots where preparatory tillage is not done.

The maximum grain equivalent yield (see table) was recorded under T6, which was superior to all treatments except T5. Relay practice and paraquat

application with different sets of minimum tillage (T1, T2, and T3) were statistically alike and ranked second. Therefore, sowing wheat in well-prepared field is advisable. If land is not ready for plowing, relay or minimum tillage are also advisable. The same trend was observed for economic return. A 150 kg ha⁻¹ seed rate was profitable irrespective of crop establishment methods. ■

Effect of wheat crop establishment method and seed rate treatment on yield and economic return in a lowland rice ecosystem. Bihar, India, 1993-95.

Treatment	Yield in terms of wheat equivalent (t ha ⁻¹)		Economic return (US\$ ha ⁻¹)		Benefit-cost ratio	
	Grain	Straw	Gross	Net		
Method of wheat crop establishment						
T1	Relay cropping (sowing in standing rice crop on 25 Nov)	4.3	5.4	572	307	2.15
T2	Paraquat application @ 2.0 kg ha ⁻¹ just after rice harvest and sowing at 24 h after that by hand plowing on 6 Dec	4.5	5.5	592	321	2.18
T3	Paraquat application, rototilling (once) and sowing behind the hand plow on 10 Dec	4.3	5.7	574	302	2.11
T4	Rototilling twice and sowing behind the hand plow on 10 Dec	4.2	5.5	554	277	2.00
T5	M.B. plow (once) + rototilling (once) and sowing behind the hand plow on 12 Dec	4.6	6.2	617	335	2.18
T6	M.B. plow (once) + rototilling twice and sowing behind the hand plow on 12 Dec	4.8	6.4	635	346	2.20
LSD (0.05)						
		0.2	0.3	26	14	0.15
Seed rate (kg ha ⁻¹)						
	S1 - 125	4.2	5.6	561	292	2.09
	S2 - 150	4.5	6.1	600	328	2.20
	S3 - 175	4.7	6.3	628	351	2.10
	LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.3	29	18	0.10

Postharvest technology

Stripper harvesting improvements meet Chinese needs

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Stripping grain, as a method of harvesting rice, was introduced into this Hangzhou institute in 1994 when we first tested the IRRI-designed SG800 system. This system represents the

Stripper-reaper system for rice harvesting.

simplest form of stripper harvesting with low intake of nongrain material in standing rice and acceptable levels of grain loss. The bulk of the straw standing in the field after stripping is unacceptable in most Chinese multi-cropping systems because it is necessary to remove the straw from the field to allow quick land preparation (1-2 d) between the first rice harvesting and second rice replanting (1-2 d).

Our work during the past 2 yr has proceeded along two lines to meet Chinese rice farmer needs. A stripper rotor placed before a reaper front (stripper-reaper system) has been fitted on a hand tractor (see figure). The appropriate distance between rotor and cutter bar is selected so the straw, after being stripped, can be cut in standing

Test results of stripper-reaper and strippercombine systems.

Item	SR-1000 system	SC-1300 system
Power (kW)	8.8	11.0
Cutting width (mm)	1000	1300
Forward speed (km h ⁻¹)	2.8-3.6	3.0-3.5
Feed rate (kg s ⁻¹)	1.1	1.3-1.4
Nongrain material (%)	12.3-17.3	3.5-4.5
Grain damage (%)	0.085	0.31
Total losses (%)	0.49-0.90	2.5-3.0
Total weight (kg)	850	1200
Estimated costs (US\$)	600	1800
Labor demand (labor-days ha ⁻¹)	4.5	2-3

position and windrowed to the side. (The stripped material feeds from stripper rotor into the tank above the reaper-front.) The engine is moved to the rear to center-balance the weight of the harvesting components. The adjust-

table skid under the engine enables the rotor to be raised or lowered, depending on crop height. Tests show that this machine has the field capacity of 1.3 ha d⁻¹ for grain harvesting and straw windrowing with grain losses less than 0.9% (see table). Estimated cost of the machine (excluding tractor) is acceptable. The wage rate of mechanical operation will be half that of the manual operation.

In 1996, we fitted a stripper rotor and conveyor on the front of a self-propelled crawler track chassis with a re-thresher and cleaner on board. The design is less labor-intensive, and is highly maneuverable in most of the wet fields in southern China. Preliminary test results of the stripper-combine system are also listed in the table. ■

Research methodology

A rapid method of isolation of genomic DNA from filamentous fungi

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This method uses fungus cultured on potato dextrose agar at 28 °C. When mat growth was visible on at least half of the plate (2-3 d), a 0.5 × 0.5 cm mycelial piece was removed with a surgical blade and placed in a 1.5-mL microfuge tube. The block was suspended in 600 µL of buffer (Tris 100 mM, pH 8.0, EDTA 150 mM, pH 8.0; NaCl 100 mM; SDS 2%; phenol 50%), and 200-300 mg of glass beads added, the contents vortexed for 3 min, and centrifuged at 13 K for 10 min. The supernatant was treated with RNase A (10-15 µg) for 15 min at 37 °C, extracted with phenol: chloroform: isoamyl alcohol (25:24:1), and the DNA precipitated with 2

volumes of absolute alcohol at room temperature. The DNA was washed with 70% alcohol and suspended in 30 µL of TE (Tris 10 mM; pH 8.0; EDTA 1 mM, pH 8.0). Genomic DNA appeared as a single, high-molecular-weight band when analyzed by a 0.8% agarose gel run in 0.5 × TBE.

To evaluate DNA prepared by this method for polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and random amplified chain, five monoconidial isolates of the rice blast fungus *Magnaporthe grisea* were analyzed. The primers used for PCR were based on the sequence of a transposable element Pot2 and the flanking target site. Two monoconidial preparations of the isolate B157 were included. The PCR was carried out in a 50-µL reaction volume of 10 mM Tris, pH 8.3; 50 mM KCl; 2.5 mM MgCl₂; 100 µM each of dATP, dCTP, dTTP, dGTP; 20 pM of each primer (17 mer); 2.5 units of Taq DNA polymerase (Perkin-Elmer); and 0.1 µg of template DNA. The thermal cycler was programmed for 94°C, 2 min denaturation followed by 35 cycles of 94 °C 1 min; 45 °C 1 min; and 72°C 2.05 min. The final extension

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification of a part of 5'-region of Pot2, an inverted repeat transposon, using the genomic DNA of two isolates of *Magnaporthe grisea* as a template. The expected size of amplification is 0.9 kb as seen in the figure. Lanes 1 and 2 represent isolates Co1043 and B101, respectively. Lanes 3 and 4 correspond to the PCR product amplified from the DNA obtained from two separate monoconidias of isolate B101. Lanes 4 and 5 also represent isolate B101, but the DNA template used in the PCR reaction was prepared using a standard method. The last lane corresponds to the kb ladder (BRL, USA) used as a molecular weight marker.